

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP7 - Communication and Dissemination

Podcast Series: “Exploring Citizen Science”

31.12.2023

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Article Series: “Exploring Citizen Science”

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I. Introduction

Summary

This report summarises the podcast series “Exploring Citizen Science” produced as part of the COESO project’s communication and dissemination activities. Included is a brief description of COESO, each of the nine podcast episodes, their publication dates, the corresponding artwork, and links to download the episodes.

COESO project overview

The COESO project (Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues)¹ is a 3-year participatory research project, funded by the European Commission through a Science with and for Society grant, and supported by the OPERAS Research Infrastructure². The COESO project contributes to overcoming the obstacles that hinder the development of citizen science in the social sciences and humanities and facilitates and supports participatory research through a service-first approach. The project develops the Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation (VERA), a collaborative place for knowledge production and sharing, and collaborates with research funding organisations to enhance financial support for citizen science. At the heart of the project are ten citizen science pilots, representing a variety of social sciences and arts disciplines, societal challenges and types of engagement with citizens in different European countries. The ten pilots address diverse specific societal issues: mass tourism, education and gender, resilient societies, fight against crime, societal change and migration, inclusivity in city planning, valorisation of ageing people in communities, accessing and using local knowledge and leadership for policy making/implementation, raising awareness on climate change, and food insecurities of children. Overall, COESO serves as a meeting point between various European communities: the social sciences and humanities community, the citizen science community, as well as the open scholarly communication community. In this bridging endeavour, COESO is synergising with existing communities such as Hypotheses.org³ and EU-Citizen.Science⁴. Moreover, it is exploring the frontiers of innovation in the social sciences and humanities’ public engagement through mutual learning exercises with the pilot projects and through experimentations with multimedia research outputs. Furthermore, to measure the quality of collaboration between researchers and citizens, COESO is designing a framework and corresponding code for a tool called *Cooperation Analytics*. More about the COESO project can be found on the project website: coeso.hypotheses.org.

Within the COESO project, the communication and dissemination work package (WP7) facilitates engagement with stakeholders to communicate the project results and outputs through a variety of communication channels, including the “Exploring Citizen Science” podcast series, which showcases COESO activities and outputs, especially those related to the pilot projects and the VERA hub.

¹ See <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006325>

² See <https://www.operas-eu.org/>

³ See <https://hypotheses.org/>

⁴ See <https://eu-citizen.science/>

II. Podcast

COESO consortium partner Bulle Media created the podcast series, “Exploring Citizen Science: can research and society be reconnected” in fulfilment of the COESO task 7.4, “Realisation of Podcasts and Articles series”.

The podcast episodes were developed and recorded between January 2022 and July 2023 in collaboration with Bulle Media and the COESO coordination team. The production involved on-site and remotely organised interviews, mostly with select COESO pilot project members, COESO consortium members.

The podcast was conceptualised as an experimental non-fiction reportage podcast about citizen-science for the purpose of disseminating to a general audience about what citizen-science is and why it matters, with a focus in particular citizen science on citizen science in the social sciences and humanities, as seen through the lenses of the researchers, project managers and citizens involved in the COESO project, and mediated by a first-person journalist's narration.

“Exploring Citizen Science” was written as a kick-off series that leaves the window open for a potential continuation of the podcast in the future. The first six episodes work as an introduction to citizen science, focusing on social sciences and humanities. The COESO team or another team might continue to host interviews in the future, or share the results of particular projects.

Bulle Media producers involved in the project:

- Alexander Damiano Ricci - senior producer, scriptwriter and host
- Claudia Torrisi - assistant producer and reporter
- Jeremy Bocquet - sound editor and designer
- Thomas Kusberg - soundtrack producer
- Antoine Lheureux - executive producer

(Podcast artwork used for thumbnail on listening platforms)

The podcast cover artwork was created in-house by Bulle Media.

Podcast synopsis

Before beginning the research and production of the podcast episodes, the following conceptual synopsis was written by Bulle Media and agreed upon by the COESO project WP7 leader and the project coordinator:

An experienced journalist and podcaster who previously worked also for a research project in the field of political science (Alexander D. Ricci) is tasked to produce a podcast series about the COESO project. Alexander takes up the challenge knowing that since a while, citizens and political parties across different national contexts, have been expressing ‘critical’ views of academia and, more generally, expert-voices and scientific knowledge: the rhetoric goes that scientists and researchers, often detached from citizens’ everyday concerns, appear like living in an ivory tower, if not serving the status-quo.

However, Alexander realises that, beyond the topics dealt with throughout the COESO research project, the mission of the researchers behind the project is truly a matter of philosophy of science. The researchers and project managers of COESO are indeed on a mission to change the way we think about social sciences. They are on a mission to let funders, NGOs and academia realise the power of citizen science.

But what is citizen science? And why does it matter today in our societies? Can it really have an impact on the way we understand our world? Can it really close the gap between lay people and science?

Alexander goes on a European audio trip to answer these questions, starting off with a conversation with Alessia Smaniotto, project coordinator of COESO, in Paris. Thanks to the interaction with Alessia, Alexander digs into the subject of philosophy of science, and engages in chats and talks with researchers of the COESO project as well as with stakeholders.

Podcast description (as published on listening platforms):

The following is the podcast description found on listening platforms:

“Exploring Citizen Science is a podcast that explores the world of Citizen Science, as a discipline and philosophy. Host and journalist Alexander Damiano Ricci travels across Europe and holds interviews with researchers and project managers who are part of the COESO research project. Alexander Damiano embarks on this journey driven by the feeling that, over the past few years, science and experts appear to have experienced a sort of backlash from society. In fact, the host believes that many citizens distrust experts and scientific knowledge out front. Yet, the discipline of Citizen Science says it aims at opening the doors of science to everyone. Within Citizen Science projects citizens can become knowledge producers themselves, just like researchers. So the question is: can Citizen Science help to (re)connect research and society?”

Episode Descriptions (as published on listening platforms)

In total, one trailer and nine podcast episodes were produced. The following descriptions for these are published on podcast platforms, as listed in the part III Dissemination Overview of this document.

Trailer (1 min 47 sec) [download link](#)

No trailer description is published. The trailer introduces the podcast topic and the narrator, Alexander Damiano Ricci. The description lists the following resources:

The COESO website: <https://coeso.hypotheses.org/>

The VERA platform: <https://vera.operas-eu.org/>

Episode 1: The ivory tower (13 min 47 sec) [download link](#)

Date published: January 10, 2023

“Alexander introduces himself and explains why his name is on the podcast: he shares the widespread criticism of academia and scientists through the “ivory tower” metaphor, to which he can relate to based on previous experiences in significant research projects. He argues about how the topic is relevant, sharing news items from political speeches and rhetoric, i.e. anti-elitism and “anti-scientism”. Therefore, he outlines the critical mission of COESO as well as starts asking questions about the latter: what is citizen science? And why does it matter today in our societies? Can it have an impact on the way we understand our world?”

Episode 2: Entering the rabbit hole (28 min 54 sec) [download link](#)

Date published: January 10, 2023

“Puzzled by the relevance of citizen science, Alexander calls Alessia Smaniotto - project coordinator of COESO. They talk about Alessia’s job and, more generally, about Philosophy of science. Therefore citizen science and COESO. Alessia answers the questions the first episode ends with.”

Episode 3: About pilots and blank stares (18 min 36 sec) [download link](#)

Date published: January 11, 2023

“After having better understood what citizen science is and why it matters in theory, Alexander continues his chat with people from COESO to understand how the project is structured and what its aims are. He talks to Kelly Achenbach, Head of communications at COESO and Alessia Smaniotto.”

Episode 4: In Lisbon - part 1: Easier said than done (14 min 16 sec) [download link](#)

Date published: April 20, 2023

“After much conversation from remote, it’s time to go on the ground and discover practices of citizen science. Alexander’s colleagues, Jeremy Bocquet (creative director and sound engineer) and Claudia Torrisi (freelance collaborator) fly to Lisbon and interview researchers and activists involved in pilot 1 of the COESO project: “Mass tourism’s impact on urban communities”

Episode 5: In Lisbon - part 2: Citizen science hands-on (25 min 14 sec) [download link](#)

Date published: April 20, 2023

“The first conversations collected by Alexander’s colleagues on the overall logic of COESO’s pilot 1 —“Mass tourism’s impact on urban communities” —left him wondering how citizens perceived the project. In this part 2 of the Lisbon chapter, citizens who took part in citizen science activities share their views on tourism and citizen science practices. Was the pilot a success story?”

Episode 6: Lunch boxes, video games and more (19 min 1 sec) [download link](#)

Date published: June 13, 2023

“After the “Lisbon experience”, Alexander goes on to talk to researchers and project managers of other pilot projects of COESO. The interviews he runs reveal the wide scope citizen-science can achieve.”

Episode 7: Too good to be VERA (17 min 28 sec) [download link](#)

Date published: June 13, 2023

“After having explored an array of citizen science projects in the field of humanities and social sciences, Alexander wonders what will stay after COESO. So he goes on the trails of VERA: an online platform with the aim of enabling a collaborative build-up of citizen science in and with social sciences and the humanities projects. VERA was built in the context of COESO and should embody the project’s long-term legacy.”

Episode 8: On Planet European Commission (30 min 48 sec) [download link](#)

Date published: June 13, 2023

“In the previous episodes of Exploring Citizen Science, Alexander analysed what citizen science is from a theoretical stand-point. Also, he looked at projects on the ground. Eventually, he tried to understand the long-term legacy COESO could bear for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). But as the first series of Exploring Citizen Science is coming closer to its end, he now wonders about the reasons why all of this - COESO and the focus on citizen science in SSH—is happening right now. And, most importantly, who is behind it. In this episode, Alexander uncovers the investment strategy of the European Commission into citizen science.”

Episode 9: The show must go on (18 min 40 sec) [download link](#)

Date published: July 12, 2023

“In the last episode of this first season of Exploring Citizen Science, Alexander wraps up the content of the project. But more importantly, he tries to answer the questions he set out originally, in episode 1. So: can citizen science help restore trust in experts in our societies? What is the “responsibility” of scientists themselves in this process and does citizen science change their perspective? How can we - meaning institutions, but maybe anyone - help citizen science grow as a practice?”

III. Dissemination

Overview of dissemination actions

“Exploring Citizen Science: can research and society be (re)connected?” is hosted on Acast and is available across a range of podcast listening apps and websites, including Spotify, Apple Podcast, Deezer, Amazon Music, Samsung, Podcast Index and others.

Information about the podcast is available on the COESO website through a blogpost, [“A new year. A new podcast”](#), and on the dedicated [COESO website media page](#). As the podcast specifically covers the COESO pilot projects, the pilot members were encouraged to spread information about the podcast through their various networks channels, and all COESO

consortium members were encouraged to add the podcast link to their email signatures. The podcast was promoted via a “smartlink” (<https://podfollow.com/exploring-citizen-science>), which automatically takes listeners to the listening platform they typically use, on newsletter contributions, dedicated social media posts on the COESO X/Twitter account, as well as at various in-person events – through specific points within verbal presentations and physical distribution of printed “seed cards” and stickers, including at:

- ECSA conference Berlin, Germany (September 2022)
- Open Science Festival in Rotterdam, The Netherlands (August 2023)
- COESO Mutual Learning Exercises 2023, Marseille, France (June 2023)
- Open Science Fair, Madrid, Spain (September 2023)
- Connect.Collaborate.Create final conference, Paris, France (October 2023)
- Falling Walls, Berlin, Germany (November 2023)
- Munin Conference, Tromsø, Norway (November 2023)

[Image of podcast sticker (size: A7)]

Statistics

As of December 13, 2023, the podcast episodes, cumulatively, have been downloaded a total of 1,798 times, broken down by episode as follows:

Episode	Downloads	% of total
Trailer	377	20.97
The ivory tower	207	11.51%
Entering the rabbit hole	293	16.3%
About pilots and blank stares	534	29.7%
In Lisbon - part 2: Citizen Science hands-on	71	3.95%

Lunch boxes, videogames and more	46	2.56%
Too good to be VERA	49	2.73%
On Planet European Commission	92	5.12%
The show must go on	59	3.28%

The podcast series is available through a variety of apps and websites and the number of downloads from each location is broken down as follows.

App	Downloads	% of total
Samsung Podcasts	528	33.26%
Spotify	371	20.62%
Chrome	349	19.41%
Apple Podcasts	147	8.18%
Other	74	4.12%
Firefox	73	4.06%
Pocket Casts	52	2.89%
Safari	43	1.78%
Google Podcasts	32	1.78%
Acast embed-player	31	1.72%

Website	Downloads	% of total
Europod.eu	223	46.17%
open.spotify.com	198	40.99%
shows.acast.com	30	6.21%
google.com	10	2.07%
podcasts.google.com	7	1.45%
stage.europod.eu	5	1.04%
stitcher2.acast.com	3	0.62%
embed-standalong.spotify.com	1	0.21%
feeds.acast.com	1	0.21%
new.europod.eu	1	0.21%

Finally, the following graphs show the distribution of downloads by date and geographic location.

Downloads

Sep 28, 2022 – Dec 12, 2023 · All episodes

Daily Weekly Monthly ↓ Export

Downloads by location

Sep 28, 2022 – Dec 12, 2023 · All episodes

